

Environmental Legal Relationships During The Covid-19 Pandemics: Challenges And Reality

Liubchych Anna¹, Savchuk Olena² & Tychyna Viktoriia³

Abstract.

The consequences of the coronavirus respiratory infection in terms of its impact on environment are analyzed in the article. Current legislation concerning medical wastes is analyzed along with the role and the place of medical wastes. Ways of solving problems on the legislation level that arose in the area of wastes handling are offered.

Keywords: environment, environmental legal relationships, pandemics.

1.Introduction.

The entire world was unprepared for the pandemics which began in 2019 and was named Covid-19, Ukraine being no exception. The pandemics has affected every facet of life, including ecologic environment in general. Nowadays, quarantine limitations and the need in individual protection (disposable masks, containers from antibacterial material, etc.) poses a considerable problem of wastes management. At the same time, of urgent importance is also the problem of handling and management of medical wastes.

Correspondence: anna.n.l@ukr.net

¹ PhD, Scientific Secretary of Institute, Scientific and Research Institute of Providing Legal Framework for the Innovative Development National Academy of Law Sciences of Ukraine, Kharkiv, ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6492-4179>

² PhD, Associate Professor of the department of Law (702) National Aerospace University H.E. Zhukovsky «Kharkiv Aviation Institute», Kharkiv, Ukraine, ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3299-7936>

³ PhD, Associate Professor of Department of Law and Law Enforcement Activities of Zhytomyr Polytechnic State University, Zhytomyr, Ukraine, ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5037-9109>

The issue of wastes handling has always been in the scope of scientists and lawmakers' attention. On the legislation level in Ukraine, this item is regulated by the Law of Ukraine "On Wastes", the Law of Ukraine "On Main Principles (the Strategy) of the State Ecology Policies till 2030", the Decree by the MOZ (the Ministry of Healthcare) of Ukraine "On Approval of Rules of Medical Means' Utilization and Destruction" of March 24, 2015 No. 242, the MOZ of Ukraine Decree "On Approval of the State Sanitary and Counter-epidemic Rules and Norms concerning Medical Wastes Handling" of June 8, 2015 No. 325, the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine Resolution "On Approval of the National Strategy of Wastes Handling in Ukraine till 2030" of November 8, 2017 No. 820-r.

2. Legal foundations.

Therefore, in the Law of Ukraine "On Main Principles (the Strategy) of the State Ecology Policies till 2030" [1] the issue of wastes is treated in great detail. According to the mentioned law, it is stressed that significant amounts of the accumulated wastes in Ukraine and the lack in efficient measures targeted at prevention of their production, recycling, utilizing, detoxication, and ecologically safe disposal deepen the ecological crisis and become an impeding factor for the national economy development. A considerable resource potential is being lost with the simultaneous worsening of already unfavorable ecology environment. Also, it is accentuated in the document on the absence of efficient control, which leads to mass-scale appearing of unsanctioned wastes-piles and numerous violations of legislation when handling hazardous wastes. With there being no separate collecting of household wastes, the problem of handling dangerous wastes contained in household wastes is not being solved in practice.

An important normative and legal act to determine attaining efficient results in legal regulation within the waste handling sphere is the Verkhovna Rada (Supreme Council) of Ukraine Resolution "On the Situation with Observing the Legislation concerning Wastes Handling in Ukraine and Ways to Improve It", which criticized the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine activities concerning ensuring efficiency of state policies in wastes handling, the improvement of normative and legal base of organizing-and-economy

mechanism to stimulate business activity in waste handling as a secondary material resources, state management in organizing of wastes collecting, recycling and utilizing as secondary material resources [2].

In this connection, V.A. Zuyev stresses that a considerable share of the measures, provided for by this Resolution, have never been accomplished, and they still remain landmarks for state policies in the wastes handling sphere [3]. Therefore, quite appropriate in this aspect was the adoption of the National Strategy of Waste Handling in Ukraine till 2030 [4], which provides for the following: 1) formation of an efficient system of collecting and removal of household wastes; 2) formation of the infrastructure for processing of household wastes; 3) formation of the infrastructure for recycling of household wastes.

4. Medical wastes.

As for medical wastes proper, it should be said that they are wastes generated by medical treatment-and-prevention facilities and other healthcare institutions that conduct medical intrusions regardless of the ownership form, as well as by spa treatment establishments, chemist's shops, science-and-research institutions, and medical training facilities. 75 to 80% of wastes generated by healthcare facilities do not contact with patients' biological fluids, infected patients, and are similar by their composition to household wastes, namely glass (bottles, containers, jars, etc.), paper, stationery, package, furniture, discarded soft staffs (medical gowns, bedlinen), and diagnostics equipment that has lost its consumer properties. The other 10 to 25% of the medical wastes pertain to the category of hazardous wastes and can pose danger for the environment and human health [5].

In the international practices of handling medical wastes from hospitals, polyclinics, and other medical institutions, the aforementioned wastes are referred to a separate group and according to the Basel Convention (1998) they are classified as hazardous wastes. The convention specifies as to which should be considered as medical wastes and where they are generated. The medical wastes include used syringes, medical gloves, contaminated blood and other body fluids, parts of skin and organs, outdated medicines, etc. This Convention also classifies medical wastes by the extent of their danger, namely: safe, that can be

removed to rubbish piles along with other wastes; epidemically hazardous (used medical instruments, laboratory wastes, etc.), which have to be disinfected and transferred to specialized enterprises; toxicologically hazardous (medicines, mercury-containing substances, etc.) that also have to be disinfected and transferred to enterprises specializing in hazardous wastes processing; radiologically hazardous wastes that need to be sent to specialized enterprises that operate nuclear wastes storages [6].

The problem of management and disinfecting of pharmaceutical wastes that have been accumulated by the population in Ukraine currently remains unregulated. The population is not informed about the danger that arises due to incorrect handling of medical wastes. Also, there is no information for the public on the possible ways to neutralize poor quality and expired medicines at home, and, most importantly, there have been created no conditions for accepting medical wastes from the population for further directing them to specialized organizations which are licensed to handle hazardous wastes [7].

5. Conclusion.

Therefore, medical wastes pertain to hazardous wastes and require a certain procedure for handling them due to their being ecologically unfriendly for the environment and people's health and well-being. Considering the extremely rapid growth rates in amounts of such wastes caused by the pandemics and the impossibility for governing bodies to react to such increase quickly enough, the authors think it necessary to offer the following measures to be implemented on the national level:

First, to form an efficient mechanism to ensure proper implementation of state policies in the sphere of hazardous wastes handling.

Second, to ensure public awareness concerning wastes handling, to conduct education work as to possible outcomes of careless attitude for the environment and humankind in general.

Third, to open accessible for public delivery points for collecting, recycling, and utilization of household wastes.

6. References

1. “On Main Principles (the Strategy) of the State Ecology Policies till 2030”. The Law of Ukraine of 28.02.2019 No. 2697-VIII. *The Bulletin of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine of 19.04.2019*. No. 16, p.70.
2. “On the Situation with Observing the Legislation concerning Wastes Handling in Ukraine and Ways to Improve It”. The Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine Resolution No. 2967-IV of 06.10.2005. *The Bulletin of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine*. 2005. No. 49, p.525.
3. Zuyev, V.A. (2014). Current ecology policies in wastes handling in Ukraine. *The Bulletin of the Academy of Tax Service of Ukraine*. Vol. “Law”. 1, pp. 93-99.
4. Savchuk, O.O. & Zayika, A.V. (2019). Problems of legal regulation of household wastes handling in Ukraine. *Support for entrepreneurship and innovation economy in the EU, Latvia and Ukraine law: II International Intersectoral Conference*. Riga: Baltic International Academy. pp. 94-99.
5. What are the basic mistakes in medical wastes handling and how to avoid them? *The Ecology of an Enterprise*. 5, 2018. [Electronic resource]. Access mode: <http://ecolog-ua.com/news/yaki-golovni-pomylky-vpovodzhenni-z-medychnymy-vidhodamy-ta-yak-yih-unyknuty>.
6. Yakovleva, Ya.S. (2019). Legal regulation of medical wastes utilization in Ukraine. *The legal system reforming in the context of euro-integrational processes: The III International Science-and-practical Conference materials*. (Sumy, May 23-24, 2019). Vol. 1. Sumy. pp. 83-86.
7. Stalinska, I. (2018). The ecological safety issues in medical wastes utilization. *The Science Bulletin of the NLTU of Ukraine*. 2018, Vol. 28, No. 2, pp. 91-94.